

Research Paper

**Delineation of Flooded Areas using Remote Sensing
Technology
A Case Study on Subarnarekha River Basin, Odisha, India**

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Abstract

Floods in India are extremely frequent owing to their geographical position. Recently, the formation of Cyclone Yaas over the Bay of Bengal struck the Indian state of Odisha, causing severe devastation to a larger extent. This study aimed at developing a methodology for rapid mapping of potential flood-affected areas exploiting Sentinel-1 synthetic aperture radar data through the usage of ground range detected images to mitigate the extent of flood damage and make a quick response. Sentinel-1 images from Pre-flood date: May 17, 2021 (The Archive Image) and post-flood date: May 29, 2021 (The crisis Image) were used from pre-processed products made available by the European Space Agency (ESA), which can be quickly treated for information extraction through different algorithms. Flooded areas appeared in red as there was a high response in the red channel but a low response in both the green and blue channels. Uniformly dark return given that will have a low backscatter return both in the archive and crisis image for which in red, green, and blue have a lower response. Finally, flood maps could be distributed to the local community to expedite aid in flood-prone areas. The data and methodology of the study could be replicated from time to time for flood mapping with high precision of flood-affected areas as the European Space Agency (ESA) offers free products i.e., systematically archived data for 24h with a high repetition rate (six days) to the public for flood analysis.

Keywords

Flood Mapping, Remote Sensing, Disaster Management, SAR, Sentinel-1, Cyclone Yaas

INTRODUCTION

Floods are one of the most severe natural hazards that cost maximum damage in contrast to other natural calamities (Dhar & Nandargi, 2003). In terms of damage to economies, infrastructure, and lives, it stunned people worldwide several times in the past decade (Amitrano, et al., 2018). During the period 1995-2015, it cost about \$662 billion with catastrophic destruction in the lives of about 2.3 billion

people (UNISDR & CRED, 2015). The consequence of this natural phenomenon has been exacerbated in Asia in comparison with other continents which is struck by 70% of all floods occurring over the world and the average annual cost is approximately \$15 billion including the immense loss in infrastructure facilities (Hansson, et al., 2008). Currently, India upholds the 18th rank in terms of coastal length and these densely populated coastal areas are extremely vulnerable due to sea-level rise, storm surges, and tropical cyclones (Ravinder Dhiman, et al., 2019). On May 26, 2021 “cyclone Yaas” which is formed over the Bay of Bengal hit Odisha, India which is the 96th tropical cyclone to strike Odisha in 130 years (Mohanty, 2021). Many areas have been flooded with serious landfall leaving roadblocks and local inhabitants isolated (Davies, 2021). It is cumbersome to protest a natural phenomenon like floods but an effective assessment of flood hazard and vulnerability to delineate flooded areas can mitigate its exposure as a crucial output for decision-makers and authorities for exigency response (Buehler, et al., 2006) (Rosser, et al., 2017). During the flood period, it is difficult to get higher accuracy from optical images for dense cloud coverage which is needless to say, a sturdy impediment for mapping (Uddin, et al., 2019). Therefore, the use of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) is getting popular nowadays for its creation of major opportunities for flood extent monitoring in all weather conditions due to the availability of the acquisition independently from solar illumination (Greifeneder, et al., 2014). This computational method provides reliable results especially for the areas with simple flood situations and homogenous topographical characteristics (Amitrano, et al., 2018). Detection of abrupt changes to land surfaces due to flood events is of utmost importance for rapid monitoring which can be efficiently performed based on multi-temporal SAR images by masking out some permanent water bodies (Mason, et al., 2012) (Zhao, et al., 2019). The Sentinel-1 mission includes two satellites (S-1A and S-1B, each carrying an imaging C-band SAR instrument providing data continuity of ERS and ENVISAT SAR types of mission) operated by the European Space Agency (ESA) which offers free products especially GMES Ocean, Land and Emergency services within 3h of acquisition for near-real-time (NRT) emergency response and 24 h for systematically archived data with a high repetition rate (six days) to the public for flood analysis (Uddin, et al., 2019) (Torres, et al., 2012) (Zhang, et al., 2020). The purpose of the study is to delineate the flooded areas of Odisha along Subarnarekha River Basin due to the recent natural event “Cyclone Yaas”.

Figure 1 EXTENT OF STUDY AREA (SUBARNAREKHA RIVER BASIN, ODISHA, INDIA)

METHODOLOGY

For delineation of flooded areas, Sentinel-1 level-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) products were used from both the archive image (pre-flood date -17 May 2021) and the crisis image (post-flood date- 29 May 2021) which were downloaded from the Copernicus open access hub data portal of the European Space Agency (ESA) (www.scihub.copernicus.eu). The GRD products consist of focused SAR data that was detected, multi-looked, and projected to the ground range using the WGS-84 Earth ellipsoid model (Uddin, et al., 2019) through some pre-processing steps including data import, radiometric calibration, speckle filtering, radiometric terrain correction, linear-to-backscattering coefficient decibel scaling (dB) transformation, and data export using ESA's Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP) (Small, 2011) (Ajadi, et al., 2016).

Figure 2 SENTINEL-1 LEVEL-1 GROUND RANGE DETECTED (GRD) PRODUCTS WITH 10M RESOLUTION. (A) ARCHIVE IMAGE (PRE-FLOOD DATE -17 MAY 2021) AND (B) THE CRISIS IMAGE (POST-FLOOD DATE- 29 MAY 2021). DOWNLOADED FROM THE COPERNICUS OPEN ACCESS HUB DATA PORTAL OF THE EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY (ESA)

Firstly, two products from different dates were first imported into “SNAP Desktop” tool and therefore cropped into the particular extent of Odisha, India by creating a raster subset for two images. Secondly, the radiometric correction was performed by applying calibration on both Sentinel-1 images to for making a comparison between the two images. Most of the pixels were found out with a very low backscatter value and few pixels were with a very high backscatter value for which a radiometric conversion from a linear scale to a dB scale was conducted for better visualization and easier to manipulate histogram (where one peak corresponds to the pixels over land and the smaller peak corresponds to the pixels over water) using the following expressions:

$$\sigma_{dB} = 10. \log_{10} \sigma^0$$

Here,

σ_{dB} = backscattering image in dB

σ^0 =Sigma nought image

After that, geometrical terrain collection was performed for projecting the pixels onto a map system inlining with correction for distortion over the areas of terrain using the Range-Doppler Terrain correction process. Then, the overlay of one image into another was done by

coregistration (Stack tool) using product geolocation. Finally, an RGB image was produced from the stacked image for a clear distinction between permanent water bodies and the flooded areas by selecting archive image as Red band and crisis image as Green and Blue band in RGB Image Channels.

Figure 3 GENERAL WORKFLOW. THE INPUT IS TWO SENTINEL-1 GRD PRODUCTS WITH 10 METERS SPATIAL RESOLUTION (PRE AND POST-FLOOD EVENT IMAGES) WHICH ARE PROCESSED WITH CROSS-CALIBRATED USING THE VARIABLE AMPLITUDE LEVEL EQUALIZATION METHOD. A CHANGE INDEX IS DEFINED TO DELINEATE THE FLOODED AREAS BY OVERLAYING TWO IMAGES.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

2.7. Result

A high radar response was found over the flooded areas in red channel as these areas would be land but it was not expected to see flooded areas in the archive image for which a high backscatter return was found out. However, over the flooded areas will have a low backscatter return in crisis image. Flooded areas appeared in red as there was a high response in the red channel but a low response in both the green and blue channels. Uniformly dark return given that will have a low backscatter return both in archive and crisis image for which in red, green and blue have a lower response. There were found some areas in cyan color

which was ground cover but not related to flooded areas. The river was appeared very dark and its surrounding areas were symbolized as different tones of grey.

Figure 4 FLOOD HAZARD MAP FOR THE STUDY AREA (SUBARNAREKHA RIVER BASIN, ODISHA, INDIA). DERIVED FLOOD MAP FOR 29 MAY, 2021 FROM SENTINEL-1 SATELLITE IMAGE.

2.8. Discussion

The method applied for delineation of flooded areas in this research from SAR data can perform well in other regions with high sustainability (Zhang, et al., 2020). The accuracy of obtained results can be enhanced by field observations. The concern over the increase of flood hazards with the growth of flood events is getting high nowadays globally (Zadeh, et al., 2020). So, it is of utmost importance to shape flood risk management policy due to the high exposure of people living in riverain and coastal areas with the rise of flood risk with the implication of proper flood hazard assessment (Golnaraghi, et al., 2020) for mitigation of aftermath of a flood.

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